

EXPLORING CONSUMER AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION OF DEPARTMENTAL STORES

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Abstract

The retail sector in India is the largest of all sectors, accounting for more than 10% of the country's GDP and about 8% of jobs. As one of the most competitive and fast paced markets, the retail industry in India has emerged with many players joining the market. In terms of format and customer purchasing behavior, the overall paradigm and definition of shopping have undergone an attention-grabbing transition, ushering in a shopping revolution in India. As is seen in the form of busy shopping centers, multi-story malls, and the vast complexes that deliver shopping, entertainment, and food all under one roof, new retail has joined the retail sector in India.

Department stores are often classified according to the kinds of goods they carry and the prices they charge; typical categories include discount, general merchandise, fashion or high fashion, and specialty. Many offers additional services, including gift wrapping, alterations, delivery, and personal shopping.

Keywords: Department stores, Perception.

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Introduction

Departmental shops have undergone major improvements as well. In the early 1900s, among other items, stores existed to sell essentials, including military uniforms, food, and clothing. Big box retailers are trying to thrive today. The growth of the internet and the rise of retail sales has put a huge burden on department stores. While several distributors have filed for bankruptcy and quit the company, others have taken dramatic action to keep afloat.

The development of department stores was linked to the growth in the 19th century of large population centres, transportation, and the harnessing of electricity for power and lighting. The Bon Marché in Paris, which began as a small shop in the early 19th century, is widely considered the first department store. John Wanamaker carried the concept to the United States in 1875 by purchasing a rail-freight depot in his native Philadelphia and populating it with a collection of specialty retailers.

Departmental Stores – Origin

Aristide Boucicaut started the Bon Marche store in Paris in 1838, which by 1852 became the first department store, displaying a wide range of products in "department" under one roof at a fixed price, without haggling or bargaining, with a "money back guarantee" allowing exchanges and refunds, employing up to 4,000 with daily sales of \$ 300,000. Alexander Stewart built his Marble Palace at Broadway and Chambers Street in New York City in 1848, a much larger version of his 283 Broadway try goods store that he started in 1823. Stewart built a true Broadway department store in 1862 with 8 floors on 2.5 acres, to 2000 employees. "Silks" and "dress wares" and toys and sports were included in the 19 departments.

Functions of Retailing

In the new business situation, retailers are key players. To appeal to India's rising middle class, major brands are running first to get into the 'desired retail formats. Retailers perform various tasks, such as delivering assortments, sorting, bulk splitting, making services, risk carrying, contact networks, transport and ads, and inventory keeping. They contribute greatly to increasing the profitability of the commodity and attracting customers.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the awareness and attitude of the customers towards departmental stores.
2. To analyze the perception of customers towards the purchase in departmental stores.
3. To identify the factors influencing the customers to make purchases at the departmental stores.

Research Methodology

The study is both analytical in nature. The Primary data is gathered from the customers of departmental stores as sample customers through structured questionnaires. Hence, the study is preferred to take the sample as 784 to match the population. The structured questionnaires have been used to collect the primary data among the employees. From the questionnaire received from the customers, the incomplete questionnaire is being rejected and the final sample is 736.

Source of awareness about the departmental stores

Table 1: Source of awareness

Sources of information	Yes	No
Family Members	627	108
Friends and Relatives	731	205
Co-workers	282	454
News Papers /Investment Magazines	391	345
Government Publications and Propaganda	297	439
Pamphlets/Leaflets/Brochures/ News Letters	332	404
Hoarding and Banners	345	391
Electronic Media (TV/Radio)/ Mainstream media	447	289

H₀₆: There is no significant association between customers' source of awareness about the departmental stores and their demographic profile

Table 2: Chi-square

Demographic profile	Chi-square value	Asymp.sig (2 tailed)
Gender	14.468 ^a	.000**
Age	1.871 ^a	.002**

Educational qualification	12.363 ^a	.050*
Occupation	22.584 ^a	.036*
Marital Status	40.122 ^a	.085
Type of family	36.021 ^a	.090
Residential Area	9.552 ^a	.045*
Number of Earning members in the family	25.402 ^a	.013**
Family Monthly Income	04.365 ^a	.066

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected for these variables and concluded that there is a significant association between the source of awareness about the departmental stores and the demographic profile of consumers viz, gender, age educational qualification, occupation, residential area, and number of earning members in the family.

Awareness about the departmental stores

Table 3: Awareness

Statements	Not Aware	Just I Know	I have Moderate Knowledge	I Know about it Full	I have Expert Knowledge	Total
The departmental stores are always conveniently located	29	28	69	292	318	736
The departmental stores are convenient for all shopping needs	29	88	53	376	190	736
The departmental stores offer reasonable/affordable prices in the area	29	44	98	288	277	736
The products sold in departmental stores are a good value for the money	28	61	78	325	244	736
The departmental stores save time by buying all items at one place	44	53	71	283	285	736
The layout at the store makes it easy to find needed items	39	49	77	352	219	736
Variety of substitutes is available in case the needed product is not available	14	60	85	268	309	736
The store gives customers individual attention	29	25	92	335	255	736
The departmental stores provide good after sales service	23	27	115	274	297	736
The departmental stores provide convenient parking	28	31	95	361	221	736

The table above expresses the customers' awareness about the departmental stores. The table confers both the frequency and percentage of their responses that range between Not aware, Just I Know, I have Moderate Knowledge, I know about it full and I have Expert Knowledge of the awareness about the departmental stores. A majority of 318 customers have expert knowledge of the departmental stores are always conveniently located, 376 customers have know about it full of the departmental stores are convenient for all shopping needs, 288 customers have known about it full of The departmental stores offers reasonable/affordable prices in the area, 325 customers have known about it full of the products sold in departmental stores are a good value for the money, 285 customers have expert knowledge of the departmental stores save time by buying all items at one place, 352 customers have known about it full of the layout at the store makes it easy to find needed items, 309 customers have expert knowledge of Variety of substitutes is available in case the needed product is not available, 335 customers have known about it full of the store gives customers individual attention followed by 297 customers have expert knowledge of the departmental stores provides good after sales service and 361 customers have known about it full of the departmental stores provides convenient parking.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
The departmental stores are always conveniently located	736	1.86	1.007	1.447	.090
The departmental stores are convenient for all shopping needs	736	2.17	1.065	1.035	.090
The departmental stores offer reasonable/affordable prices in the area	736	1.99	1.051	1.139	.090
The products sold in departmental stores are a good value for the money	736	2.05	1.054	1.102	.090
The departmental stores save time by buying all items at one place	736	2.03	1.145	1.186	.090
The layout at the store makes it easy to find needed items	736	2.10	1.066	1.185	.090
Variety of substitutes is available in case the needed product is not available	736	1.92	1.013	1.082	.090
The store gives customers individual attention	736	1.96	.981	1.294	.090
The departmental stores provide good after sales service	736	1.92	.991	1.161	.090
The departmental stores provide convenient parking	736	2.03	.970	1.228	.090
Valid N (listwise)	736				

Source: Primary data

The above table depicts the descriptive statistics of the awareness about the departmental stores among the customers. It can be concluded from the table that the statement The departmental stores are convenient for all shopping needs has the better mean at 2.17 and the statement The departmental stores save time by buying all items at one place has the better standard deviation at 1.145.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their gender.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their gender.

Table 5: Chi-Square Tests - Gender			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.854 ^a	8	.045*
Likelihood Ratio	19.118	8	.014*
Linear-by-Linear Association	.056	1	.812
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .34.			

*Significant at 5 percentage level. **Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 5 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their gender. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 15.854, which is significant (0.045) at 5 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their gender.

Association between the customers' age and awareness about the departmental stores

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their age.

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests - Age			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	158.277 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	107.718	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	67.531	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 6 cells (30.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.10.			

*Significant at 5 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 6 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their age. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 158.277, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their age.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their educational qualification.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their educational qualification.

Table 7: Chi-Square Tests - Educational Qualification			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	112.621 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	125.561	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.084	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 5 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.18.

**Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 7 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their educational qualification. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 112.621, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their educational qualification.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their occupation.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their occupation.

Table 8: Chi-Square Tests - Occupation			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	151.488 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	138.749	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.522	1	.004*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 3 cells (15.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.36.

*Significant at 1 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 8 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their occupation. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 151.488, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their occupation.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their marital status.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their marital status.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	99.828 ^a	8	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	73.559	8	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.778	1	.052*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 3 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.33.

*Significant at 1 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 9 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their marital status. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 99.828, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their marital status.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their type of family.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their type of family.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	33.848 ^a	4	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	50.707	4	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.983	1	.005*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.98.

*Significant at 1 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 10 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their type of family. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 33.848, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their type of family.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their residential area.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their residential area.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	87.267 ^a	8	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	94.467	8	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	29.231	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.77.

**Significant at 1 percentage level.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 11 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their residential area. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 87.267, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their residential area.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.576 ^a	12	.005*
Likelihood Ratio	32.058	12	.001**
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.805	1	.003*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 2 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.77.

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 12 presents the chi-square between the awareness about the departmental stores and their number of earning members in family. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 28.576, which is significant (0.005) at 5 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

Association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their family monthly income.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their family monthly income.

Table 13: Chi-Square Tests - Family Monthly Income			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	109.243 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	109.638	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	70.780	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 5 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.37.			

**Significant at 1 percentage level, *Significant at 5 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 13 presents the chi-square between awareness about the departmental stores and their family monthly income. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 109.243, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' awareness about the departmental stores and their family monthly income.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their demographic profile

H₀: There is no significant association between customers' customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their demographic profile

The hypothesis is further broken down into sub hypotheses each represents the departmental stores variables of the consumers.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their gender.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their gender.

Table 14: Chi-Square Tests - Gender			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.018 ^a	8	.015*
Likelihood Ratio	22.082	8	.005*
Linear-by-Linear Association	.971	1	.325
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .28.			

*Significant at 5 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 14 presents the chi-square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their gender. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 19.018, which

is significant (0.015) at 5 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their gender.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and age.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and age.

Table 15: Chi-Square Tests - Age			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	119.456 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	70.659	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	40.078	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 6 cells (30.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .91.			

**Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 15 presents the chi-square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and age. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 119.456, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and age.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their educational qualification.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their educational qualification.

Table 16: Chi-Square Tests - Educational Qualification			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	61.715 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	66.673	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.815	1	.178*
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 5 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .97.			

**Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 16 presents the chi-square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their educational qualification. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 61.715, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded

that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their educational qualification.

Association between the customers' purchases at departmental stores and their occupation.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' purchases at departmental stores and their occupation.

Table 17: Chi-Square Tests - Occupation			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	48.508 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	55.823	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	.836	1	.360*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 5 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.94.

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 17 presents the chi-square between purchases at departmental stores and their occupation. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 48.508, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' purchases at departmental stores and their occupation.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their marital status.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their marital status.

Table 18: Chi-Square Tests - Marital Status			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	89.278 ^a	8	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	58.714	8	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	.100	1	.752
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 3 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.09.

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 18 presents the chi-square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their marital status. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 89.278, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their marital status.

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their type of family.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their type of family.

Table 19: Chi-Square Tests - Type of Family			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.589 ^a	4	.001**
Likelihood Ratio	25.619	4	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.920	1	.000**
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.38.			

**Significant at 1 percentage level, *Significant at 5 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

The table 19 presents the chi square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their type of family. The table states that the chi square value between the variables is 89.278, which is significant (0.001) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their type of family

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data.

Association between the customers' gender and residential area towards the purchases at departmental stores.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their residential area.

Table 20: Chi-Square Tests - Residential Area			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	54.187 ^a	8	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	67.163	8	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	.025	1	.875
N of Valid Cases	736		
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.56.			

**Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

Table 20 presents the chi-square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their residential area. The table states that the chi-square value between the variables is 54.187, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their residential area.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

Table 21: Chi-Square Tests - Number of Earning Members in Family			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	66.628 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	76.456	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.644	1	.056*
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 3 cells (15.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.09.

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

The table 21 presents the chi square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their number of earning members in family. The table states that the chi square value between the variables is 66.628, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.

Association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their family monthly income.

H₀: There is no significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their family monthly income.

Table 22: Chi-Square Tests - Family Monthly Income			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	100.313 ^a	12	.000**
Likelihood Ratio	94.132	12	.000**
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.675	1	.001**
N of Valid Cases	736		

a. 4 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.13.

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

The table 22 presents the chi square between attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their family monthly income. The table states that the chi square value between the variables is 100.313, which is significant (0.000) at 1 percentage. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant association between the customers' attitude towards the purchases at departmental stores and their family monthly income.

Perception towards departmental store purchases: Tangibility

Table 23: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Clean, attractive and convenient physical facilities	736	4.20	.817	-1.039	.090
Modern and pleasing appearance	736	3.81	.841	-.817	.090
Materials associated with the stores' service are visually appealing	736	3.74	.941	-.577	.090
Products displayed with details	736	3.76	1.026	-.633	.090
Recreation area for children and hygienic toilets and protected drinking water	736	3.80	1.000	-.614	.090
The layout makes it easier for customers to move around and seek what they need	736	3.78	.957	-.698	.090
I would rate this outlet professional and competent	736	3.72	.945	-.599	.090
Valid N (listwise)	736				

Source: Primary data

The above table depicts the descriptive statistics of the Perception towards departmental store purchases: Tangibility. It can be concluded from the table that the statement Clean, attractive and convenient physical facilities has the better mean at 4.20 and the statement Products displayed with details has the better standard deviation at 1.026.

Difference between the Perception towards departmental store purchases on responsiveness and their family monthly income.

H₁: There is no significant difference between customers' Perception towards departmental store purchases on responsiveness and their family monthly income.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Responsiveness	Between Groups	.699	3	.233	.256	.857
	Within Groups	665.767	732	.910		
	Total	666.466	735			

*Significant at 5 percentage level **Significant at 1 percentage level

Source: Compiled and calculated using the primary data

The analysis of variance for the Perception towards departmental store purchases on responsiveness and their family monthly income has been presented in the above table. It is conferred that the F value being .256, having the significance of .857, stating the significance between the variables. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference between Perception towards departmental store purchases on reliability and their family monthly income.

Assurance

Table 25: Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Entertaining return and exchange of commodities	736	4.03	.852	-.581	.090
Whenever the customer has a problem, the store shows sincere interest in solving it	736	3.87	.912	-.866	.090
Employees are capable to handle customers complaints directly and immediately	736	3.79	1.048	-.771	.090
Goods/products are easily exchanged if defects are found in the quality	736	3.78	.958	-.824	.090
The cashier is readily efficient in dealing with the payment at the counter	736	3.87	.923	-.710	.090
Billing and checking out is fast	736	3.88	.884	-.693	.090
The services provided meet the needs	736	3.85	.913	-.587	.090
The employees are trustworthy	736	3.78	.906	-.961	.090
Feeling of safety in my transactions especially when the purchase is done by debit/credit cards	736	3.95	.967	-1.113	.090
Valid N (listwise)	736				

Source: Primary data

The above table depicts the descriptive statistics of the Perception towards departmental store purchases on assurance. It can be concluded from the table that the statement Entertaining return and exchange of commodities has the better mean at 4.03 and the statement Employees are capable to handle customers complaints directly and immediately has the better standard deviation at 1.048.

Findings

Source of awareness about the departmental stores

- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their gender.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their age
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their educational qualification.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their occupation.

- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their marital status.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their type of family.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their residential area.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their number of earning members in family.
- There is a significant association between the respondents' awareness about the departmental stores and their family monthly income.

Perception towards departmental store purchases: Tangibility

- The descriptive statistics of the Perception towards departmental store purchases: Tangibility. It can be concluded from the table that the statement Clean, attractive and convenient physical facilities has the better mean at 4.20 and the statement Products displayed with details has the better standard deviation at 1.026.

Suggestions

Stores must place a strong emphasis on attractive physical facilities. The ambience may be made pleasant, and the products can be exhibited quickly for effective product identification. To attract customers, it may be appreciated if the store sets reasonable pricing, i.e., below the product's MRP. Stores must focus heavily on product availability to suit client needs and desires. Customers are unwilling to wait for longer billing periods. To retain clients, the store may focus on attracting female customers by providing services such as free door delivery, taking orders via phone, SMS, or e-mail, and so on.

Conclusion

The retail sector has a wide range of business needs and service demands. Globalization, customization, and consolidation have all had a substantial impact on the traditional retail paradigm. Retailers must analyze these many issues carefully in order to grow sales and meet profit targets, and effective measures must be made as a result. Department stores must expand their space and redesign their layout. Quality can be enhanced, and a wide range of items must be offered, as well as a high level of personal care and attention, in order to attract and please client.